

Research Article**Social Justice for Indian Informal Workers****Dr. ASHOK. K. A**Associate Professor, Department of Economics, Government First Grade College, C.S.Pura,
Gubbi(Tq), Tumkur (Dist), Karnataka**Corresponding Author: Dr. ASHOK. K. A****Abstract**

Any countries economic development depends on labor force active participation, labour contribution and tireless working nature immensely contribute to economic growth. The Indian labour market is highly informal/unorganised, around 90 per cent of labours are in informal sector, contribution to national Gross Domestic Product has been falling, slow employment generation in formal sector causing to increase of labours engage in the informal works. In recent years women labour force participation in India increasing due to several female oriented works development and female inclusiveness in the economic activities are increasing, but it is meager compare to other countries women labour force participation rate, in India it is just 25 per cent, even though 95 per cent of women workers are earning their daily bread in the informal works. Informal works are Beedi rolling and cigar manufacturing, apparel designing, embroidery, oil extraction, Garment works, carpeting, candle making, packing, weaving, working in handlooms, coir industries, hotel, working in petrol pump, brick industries, making brooms, furniture, cleaners, fashion designers, performing artists, construction workers, house maids etc, these workers are not working in secured jobs, they are deprived social security, prone to exploitation, discrimination among caste, religion, inequal salaries and allowances, unhealthy working conditions and prone to hazardous diseases and life risks. Social justice is paramount important for Indian informal workforce and especially for the workers engaged in informal sector. Social Justice means gender equality at working place, Government policy supports, decent working atmosphere, social security's measures, equal pay, elimination of discrimination on the grounds caste, religion and creed, other basic amenities and government incentives and subsidies.

Keywords: Social Justice, Informal, Labour Participation, Economic Development.**Introduction:**

Any countries economic development depends on labor force active participation, labour contribution and tireless working nature immensely contribute to economic prospect, but World of work having many issues and challenges, in recent global developments, transitions in the post COVID-19, meltdown of supply chain across the world and Russian aggression on Ukrian surge of business, trade slowdown created panic in the labour market and forcefully pushed to unemployment, lack of purchasing power and distress, by these informal workforce are affected at large quantum. In 2023. Labour force participation trends returned to a pre-pandemic downward trend in Asia also. In Asia and the Pacific region, nearly two-thirds of the Jobs are informal kind of employment in the year of 2023, within this region the informality of employment rates varies considerably. In 2023, Asia was witnessed 60.9 per cent of the

labour participation, Informality of employments are highest in the south-east Asia(70 per cent), 47 per cent in east Asia and 35 per cent in the Pacific region. Informality affects the Asia and Pacific region at varying degrees for their economic growth and nature of work, created a challenge for prospect of the economic development. Labour force participation, labour force participation assess the countries Human development index. Socio-economic developments and declining of poverty in this region, educational attainment has been improved. At the same time women labour force participation in the Asian region also increased and contributing to the country economic development, specially countries like Asian tigers, India, China, Bangladesh and Taiwan are producing women manual oriented products for the world markets.

Various estimates shown that India is the fastest growing across the world, but is this growth reflected in employment generation and the quality of employment? The recent Periodic Labour Force Survey 2023-24 suggest that the labour force and workforce participation rates are increasing. For example, the workforce participation rate has risen to 43.7% from 41.1% in 2022-23, while the labour Force Participation Rate (LFPR)has increased from 42.2% in 2022-23 to 45.1% in 2023-24. The Indian labour market is highly informal or unorganised, around 90 per cent of labours are in informal sector of the Indian economy, The term unorganized worker has been defined in the “Unorganised Workers’ Social Security Act,2008, means a home-based worker, self-employed worker or a wage worker in the unorganized sector and includes a worker in the organized sector who is not covered by the Industrial Dispute Act,1947 or Chapter III to VII of the code i.e. the Unorganised or informal workers are subject to lack of a formal employer-worker relationship, absence of adequate social security protection and other welfare schemes such as sickness and unemployment allowance”, the formal sector contribution to national Gross Domestic Product has been falling, slow employment generation in formal sector causing to increase informal works, low level of skills among the educated youths still persists, education content is not supporting to employment generation, means mismatch between Indian Education system and Industrial manufacturing requirements. “Although the percentage of regular workers’ has increased along with the share of formal sector workers a significant proportion of regular workers in the formal sector are informal”. Informal works are Beedi rolling and cigar manufacturing, apparel designing, embroidery, oil extraction, Garment works, carpeting, candle making, packing, weaving, working in handlooms, coir industries, hotel, working in petrol pump, in gig works, in platform economy, brick industries, making brooms, furniture, cleaners, fashion designers, performing artists, construction workers, house maids etc, these workers are not secured and having healthy working conditions and prone to hazardous and life risks, in recent years women labour force participation in India increasing due to several female oriented development and female inclusion in the economic activities are increasing, but it is meager compare to other countries women labour force participation rate, in India it is just 25 per cent, to in this 95 per cent of women workers are earning their daily bread in the informal works, which is a reflection of gender inequalities at large scale. Indian labour market is highly segregated on different occupation, gender, social groups, different industrial location and geographical regions, although the gaps in earnings (comparatively male and women workers), across different social groups or categories. Social justice is paramount important for Indian informal workforce and especially for the women workers engaged in informal sector.

Review of Literature

International Labour Organisation and Institute for Human Development (2024), “ India Employment Report(Youth Employment, Education and Skills)” : the report enlightened the status of Employment trends and current scenario in the Indian Economy, Growth and employment, Challenge of youth employment, education and youth employment, skills and active labour market policies, skills requirement and mismatch of education and production and

executive skills in the Indian labour market, status of informal workers and the conditions and also emphasizes on social justice requirement for these informal workers.

International Labour Organization(2024) ; “ World Employment and Social Outlook”- Trends 2024 : the report focused on the resilience of world economy after the covid-19 pandemic, job growth, rising fragility, unemployment rate across the different countries, wage rate across the countries, working poverty, labour imbalances, outlook remains cloudy as a poly-crisis worsens social justice.

Patricia Cohen(2024), “Poor Nations are writing a new handbook for getting rich”, in his article focused on Economies focused on ‘exports have lifted millions out of poverty, but epochal changes in trade, supply chains and technology are making these countries a lot harder for development, labour market crisis’.

Ajit Ranade(2024), “Economic Boom, Job Bust, India’s Employment Dilemma”, he analyses the ILO-IHD report in his term, criticized the employment conditions, the labour force participation rate in India, employment status, informality of employment in the Indian Economy, the Worker Participation Ratio, women engagement in work, employment generation activities, sectorial occupation growth and contributions to the Gross Domestic Product. Mismatch between education and Production / economy requirement, skill enhancement, youth employment, demographic character and demographic dividend and its impact on Indian Economy.

Objectives of the study

1. To analyze the work nature and scope in the Indian Economy.
2. To Analyze the Informal working conditions in the Indian Economy.
3. To examine the Social Justice measures provided to informal workers in the Indian Economy.
4. To study the efficient implementation of social security services for the unorganized workers, including women workers.

Research Methodology

This research study deals with the description of the different method undertaken for the study. The present study analysis of social justice for informal workers in the Indian Economy is based on the secondary data, these data collected from the different article published in peer reviewed journals, publications of International Labor Organization, analysis of ILO-IHD (Institute for Human Development) “The Indian Employment Report-2024”, reports of Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy, World bank report, Magazine articles and News Paper articles.

Various Social Justice dimensions:

Indian Labour Market is abundantly informal, 90 per cent of the workers are working in informal works, basic required skills are the barriers to enhance productivity, efficiency and contributing for economic development of the nation, these informal workers are facing many difficulties at working place, health hazardous, over time work, absence of working place facilities, lack of social securities, job uncertainty, transportation facilities, adequate training. In India, education enrollment is not converting labour participation it is leading to unemployment, lack of skill oriented, apprentice training, irrelevant education system, technology driven job losses, women labor participation is very low comparatively to other Asian pacific countries. Labour policies should revive, skill oriented education after the higher primary level of education in India. Content of college education should modify towards skill oriented education to fulfill skill deficit in the country. To realize the Vikasith Bharath concept and to achieve the 5 trillion economy and to achieve vision-2047.

The social Justice includes the ensuring Universal Human Rights and build capability for the Indian informal sector, human rights includes the education level of the worker, social

security measures taken, health care facilities, decent working atmosphere, dignity of labor, healthy working place, equal remuneration for equal work, equal working opportunities for women workers in informal sector, provident facilities, social securities, frequent health check-up, decent working hours, free transportation, over duty remuneration, weekly one leave, adequate standard of living, right have association, training for skills acquisition. Equal treatment and equal distribution; means treat free at working place is essential to access to opportunities in informal sector, boost efficiency and productivity. Just transition of the International Labor organization is one more dimensions, transformations occurred in the Indian economy how effect on informal sector workers, it means effect on their well-being over time, example globalization, privatization, middle east war tension or geopolitical tensions, advancement in technology specially Artificial Intelligence, rate of unemployment, Indian demographic dividend, climate changes, COVID-19 crisis, Government policies and practices.

Suggestions

To achieve economic prosperity of Indian Economy social justice is most essential for the Indian informal labours. The government should promulgate social justice to the informal workers to enhance productivity, social justice covers dignity of labor, decent working atmospheres, maternity benefit facilities and monthly one leave facilities to promote active women workers participation, equal opportunities, equal wages for equal work, investment on Human Capital Development means investment on informal sector labors development increase nation productivity, various governments in India should ensure social welfare measures for informal labors, ensure adequate wages and workplace benefits for these laborers, promulgate better working environment and working conditions, promote better Human Resources Management of informal sector and Industrial Relations.

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